

FLUENCY IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AS A LINGUOMETHODICAL PROBLEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085761>

Abstract. *The phenomenon of fluency in speaking a foreign language is considered from the perspective of modern linguodidactics. Various interpretations of the concept of “speech fluency” are analyzed. Quantitative (pauses, ability to divide into syntagms, ability to fill and shorten pauses) and qualitative (range of language means used, accuracy of statements, variety of morphological forms and syntactic structures used, lexical economy, metaphorically) characteristics of speaking fluency are discussed. forming the basis for the development of a scale for its assessment.*

Keywords: *speaking fluency, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of fluency, communicative approach, rate of speech, pause, speed of speech, cognitive factors.*

INTRODUCTION

Being one of the most important qualities of coherent speech, fluency not only makes foreign language communication successful, but is an indicator of the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language. Fluency is not synonymous with spontaneity and is not reducible to speed or tempo of speech. It is an indicator of the developed ability to communicate in the target language and correctly formed speech, close to the natural speech of native speakers. The communicative approach prescribes teaching foreign language speaking in such a way that it approaches the speech of a native speaker and does not cause problems in communication, is perceived as natural, i.e. was runaway. There are many interpretations of this concept. Various characteristics of speaking fluency are given. Familiarization with different points of view allows us to conclude that we are dealing with a complex linguistic and methodological phenomenon. Along with other qualities of coherent speech, fluency allows us to talk about the effectiveness of communication in the target language and the productivity of the educational process [1–4].

METHODS

A.A. Akishina and O.E. Kogan [5] consider speech fluency as a criterion that includes some other criteria and is the final characteristic of foreign language communication at the professional level. At the same time, fluent speech is distinguished by lexical and grammatical purity, clarity, and stylistic adequacy. T.M. Balykhin and M.S. Netesin [6] see in speaking fluency the ability to create long-term spontaneous utterances in accordance with the nature of spoken language. Speech fluency, as K. Nair argues [7], is impossible without the ability to spontaneously generate statements. The point of view of N.G. seems important to Shakhtakhtinskaya, who insists that “it is necessary to abandon the interpretation of the terms “spontaneity of speech” and “speech fluency” as synonymous concepts, since the nature of the flow of so-called spontaneous speech can be high-quality and at the same time low-quality, since speech may be spontaneous, but not fluent, or fluent, but not at all spontaneous” [8]. To a large extent, fluency of speech depends on the reaction of the individual, due to his experience and ability to navigate a changing communication situation. Fluency is often confused with speed and tempo of speech. Speed and quick reaction, as rightly noted by R. Schmidt [1], are not inherent in the controlled speech process, since during a controlled utterance the pace often slows down. It slows down not only because the skills are not sufficiently automated, but also because, even

when they are automated, pauses in speech are usually associated not so much with the form as with the content of the utterance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The process of speaking is not limited to “dressing” thoughts in words and expressing thoughts in words, as L.S. emphasized. Vygotsky [2], considering it as the consistent completion of the thought itself in words. The process of speaking occurs “from the motive that gives rise to any thought, to the design of the thought itself, to its mediation in the internal word, then in the meaning of external words and, finally, in words” [4]. Speaking about the inseparability of words and concepts, you should pay attention to the following points:

1. The motive is related to the need for speaking and its subject.
2. A person begins to speak and enters into communication with another person when there is a communicative intention.
3. The word is associated with the concept.
4. Speech is a way of forming and formulating thoughts in language.
5. The word exists in the memory of speech-auditory analysis - Torah.
6. The concept and the word are updated simultaneously.

Thus, the main factors contributing to fluency in speaking a foreign language are motivated need and activity. In other words, the speaking mechanism is set in motion due to the presence of communicative intention. The connection with activity is important. The connection between a word and a concept is ensured when the area of language use is taken into account. An equally significant factor is the connection with the individual [5]. It manifests itself in the presence of a word in the individual’s consciousness and the maximum involvement of all spheres of his consciousness (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Factors influencing speaking

It is interesting in this regard to note that, noting the long nature of speech, researchers tend to consider this kind of pauses, pauses of hesitation, as an important factor in natural fluent speaking and effective communication [6]. Fluent speech is characterized by the formation of the ability to instantly make decisions when transforming information from one language level into representations at another, however, the speed of reaction does not contradict the fact that effective communication is always controlled. The controlled production of utterances keeps them consistent with communicative intentions. This is the task of speaking fluency, despite the fact that the speed of utterance may be low [2]. From the above, we can conclude that speed and ease of speech are optional characteristics of fluent speaking. According to the fair remark of A.A. Alkhazishvili [3], speaking fluency indicates the extent to which students have automated

the relevant skills in natural communicative situations. Speaking fluency is not limited to the rate of speech, which often varies from student to student. Fluent speech is speech in which there are no pauses, repetitions, etc. unjustified by the development of reasoning. A comparison of existing interpretations of speaking fluency allows us to talk about this phenomenon as a set of certain skills [6]. They are established by correlating the characteristics of speaking fluency in the native and target languages. Fluency is an indicator of the development of the ability to speak in the target language and characterizes speech as correct in pronunciation, intonation, grammatical and lexical terms, close to the natural speech of native speakers. The assessment of this indicator involves taking into account a number of characteristics that depend, on the one hand, on the number and duration of pauses, and on the other, on the type of pauses. Such characteristics are, firstly, pauses between semantic fragments of speech; secondly, the ability to divide speech into syntagms; thirdly, the ability to fill pauses and shorten them [7]. The main role in human life, as D.N. Uznadze believed [6], is played by consciousness. He is aware of his behavior in advance, resorting to this or that action only as a result of understanding the need for its implementation. L.S. Vygotsky also wrote that all learning "revolves around two processes: awareness and mastery" [3]. A foreign language is no exception in this sense. In this regard, I.P. Susov's reasoning [8] about language as one of the elements of the information-cognitive system, a kind of tool for human knowledge of the world, seems interesting. In this system we are dealing with the interaction of thinking, consciousness and language. Considering various aspects of language - cognitive, interactive, communicative, ethnocultural, social-group and personal, the researcher expresses the idea that speaking deals with the activation of typical patterns, on the one hand, of the learner's communicative and practical activity, and on the other - organization of his inner world, which are presented in his individual picture of the world and are ethnoculturally and socially determined.

CONCLUSION

All of the above aspects, as shown by the experience of using moral dilemmas in teaching speaking a foreign language, play an important role in the development of fluency in this type of speech activity. This is explained by the fact that this quality of oral speech relates to a greater extent to its qualitative characteristics than to its quantitative ones.

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